

D2.3 – Preliminary Design Report

prepared for

WP2.3 – Preliminary System Design

Version: 1.0

Published: 2023-02-28

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Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
0.1	2023-01-17	Paul Zabel	Initial document setup
0.2	2023-02-21	Paul Zabel + partner authors	Insertion of inputs from partners
1.0	2023-02-28	Paul Zabel + partner authors	Final version

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1 Introduction

1.1 Study Objectives

The LUWEX Concurrent Engineering study was aimed at tackling the following objectives:

- Performing the preliminary design of the LUWEX experimental setup.
- Determining the volume allocation and accommodation of required components.
- Defining the interfaces between the elements of the setup.
- Build up a component list for all subsystems, including costs and details regarding suppliers/manufacturers.

1.2 Reference Documents

The work of the CE-Study was based on pre-existing knowledge of the project partners and on the following two documents:

- LUWEX D2.1 System Requirements Document,
- LUWEX D2.2 Lunar Raw Water Information.

1.3 Participants and Study Domains

Figure 1-1: Group photo of the CE-Study team.

Table 1-1: LUWEX CE-Study team.

Domain	Responsible	Organization
Moderator	Antonio Martelo	DLR
Moderator	Dominik Quantius	DLR
Project coordinator	Paul Zabel	DLR
Requirements	Bob Davenport	LSG
Data Acquisition and Control	Henning Wache	DLR/TUBS
Quality and Condition Monitoring 1	Szymon Krawczuk	SW
Quality and Condition Monitoring 2	Anna Jurga and Karol Leluk	PWR
Raw Water Simulant 1	Victoria Pesch	DLR/FH Bremen

Domain	Responsible	Organization
Raw Water Simulant 2	Rieke Freer	DLR
Purification and Storage 1	Giorgio Boscheri	TAS
Purification and Storage 2	Rachele Perelli	TAS
Extraction 1	Luca Kiewiet	DLR
Infrastructure and Ice-regolith Simulant 1	Christopher Kreuzig	TUBS
Infrastructure and Ice-regolith Simulant 2	Johanna Brecher	TUBS
Capturing	Christoph Kalis	DLR/TU Delft
Extraction 2	Mart Heitkamp	DLR/Uni of Twente

1.4 Study Schedule

Time	Mo	Tue	Wed	Thur	Fr
09:00	Kick-Off Presentations Study / CEF Introduction Study Background LAB setup + TVAC Water Extraction Trade-off Purification and Storage S/S Component List (EXCEL)	Short Status Report	Short Status Report	Short Status Report	Non-Moderated Time Action Items Splinter Meetings Preparation of next Session
09:30		Non-Moderated Time Equipment list completion	Session #3.1 Define Configuration	Session #4.1 Finalisation of Experiment Schedule	
10:00	Non-Moderated Time Water Capturing Trade	Session #2.1 Overview of equipment list	Non-Moderated Time Action Items Splinter Meetings Preparation of next Session Experiment Schedule TBD	Non-Moderated Time Action Items Splinter Meetings Preparation of next Session	Final Presentations - Raw water simulant - Infrastructure and Ice-regolith Simulant - Extraction - Capturing - Purification and Storage
10:30		Session #1.1 Water Capturing Experiment Architecture			
11:00					
11:30					
12:00					
12:30					
13:00	Lunch Break	Lunch Break	Lunch Break	Lunch BreakC	Lunch Break
13:30	DLR Tour	Non-Moderated Time Data, water flow, and power interface definition at system level	Non-Moderated Time Action Items Splinter Meetings	Session #4.2 Final CAD model presentation	Final Presentations - Quality and Conditioning Monitoring - Data Acquisition and Control Requirements
14:00	Session #1.2 Domain Round Define equipment list				
14:30	Non-Moderated Time Action Items Splinter Meetings	Session #2.2 Discussion of defined interfaces	Non-Moderated Time Action Items Splinter Meetings Preparation of next Session Experiment Schedule TBD	Non-Moderated Time Action Items Splinter Meetings Preparation of next Session	Wrap-up
15:00					
15:30					
16:00					
16:30	Session #1.3 Domain Round				
17:00	Non-Moderated Time				
17:30					

Figure 1-2: CE-Study schedule as executed.

1.5 Summary per Study Day

Activity: **LUWEX CE Study – Day 1** Date: 23/01/2023

Start Time: 8:15 End Time: 18:00

- Facility use:
- Conducted CE Study kick-off presentations
 - Worked to define system equipment
 - Preliminary interface analysis performed
 - Identification of open discussion points regarding capturing method selection
 - Equipment responsibility clarified

Activity: **LUWEX CE Study – Day 2** Date: 24/01/2023

Start Time: 8:30 End Time: 18:00

- Facility use:
- System equipment identified (some key parameters not yet completed at this point)
 - Data, water flow, and power interfaces defined

Activity: **LUXWEX CE Study – Day 3** Date: 25/01/2023
 Start Time: 8:30 End Time: 18:00
 Facility use:

- Preliminary test scheduling discussed with individual team-members
- Preliminary configuration presented and discussed
- Sequence of water flux and valve system use

Activity: **LUXWEX CE Study – Day 4** Date: 26/01/2023
 Start Time: 8:30 End Time: 18:00
 Facility use:

- CATIA configuration completed and presented
- Scheduling discussed and finalised

Activity: **LUXWEX CE Study – Day 5** Date: 27/01/2023
 Start Time: 8:30 End Time: 16:00
 Facility use:

- Final discussions and presentations

2 System Overview

The LUWEX experimental setup consists of the following subsystems:

- Data Acquisition, Control and Power,
- Water Extraction,
- Water Capturing,
- Water Purification and Storage,
- Water Quality and Condition Monitoring,
- Laboratory and Experiment Infrastructure (which includes the thermal vacuum chamber (TVAC))

and the following additional components:

- Ice-Regolith Simulant,
- Raw Water Simulant.

Figure 2-1 shows a block diagram of the overall system indicating the interfaces between the different subsystems and components.

Figure 2-1: Block diagram of the overall system of the LUWEX experimental setup. Dashed arrows indicate signal and power interfaces. Solid arrows indicate water (solid, liquid or gaseous state) flow.

The preliminary design of each subsystem is described in the following chapters.

3 Requirements

SRD scope and CE study preliminary design. The SRD identifies LUXWEX system level requirements and interfaces between the subsystems TVAC and WPS and external interfaces of the subcomponents of these subsystems. The previous draft versions of the SRD identified requirements based on the LUXWEX proposal and analysis of the end-to-end process for extracting and purifying water from water ice-regolith simulant. The CE study of the preliminary design clarified many open TBDs and identified new requirements. The CE study has clarified issues with respect to the end-to-end process. For the SRD the main contribution to the SRD has been identification of the system/subsystem interfaces.

SRD status – layout

The document is structured as follows:

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There are about 70 requirements. Each requirement identifies who is responsible for implementation and how it shall be verified i.e., T, ROD, A, I.

The resulting SRD will be issued as v1.0 and delivered to EU by 31.01.2023! There are still TBDs that need to be clarified.

Issues

Do we meet the intent of the following requirement?

1.2.3 Ice-regolith simulant chemical characteristics (Original version)

The ice-regolith simulant shall contain volatiles with a composition reflecting as far as possible the LCROSS plume analysis including water, carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, hydrogen sulphide, sulphur dioxide. These molecules shall be added to the raw water prior to injection in the WPS to test the purification technology.

Note: For LCROSS plume analysis, see "Detection of Water in the LCROSS Ejecta Plume" Anthony Colaprete, et al. Science 330, 463 (2010); DOI: 10.1126/science.1186986. End of note.

[Responsible: DLR, TUBS] [Verification: T]

1.2.3 Ice-regolith simulant chemical characteristics (Updated version)

The ice-regolith simulant shall contain volatiles with a composition reflecting as far as possible the LCROSS plume analysis including water, carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, hydrogen sulphide, sulphur dioxide. These molecules shall be added to the raw water prior to injection in the WPS to test the purification technology.

Note 1: It is understood the introduction of all these molecules in the TVAC ice-regolith simulant is not recommended for the TVAC chamber due to potential damage to hardware.

Note 2: For LCROSS plume analysis, see "Detection of Water in the LCROSS Ejecta Plume" Anthony Colaprete, et al. Science 330, 463 (2010); DOI: 10.1126/science.1186986. End of note.

[Responsible: DLR, TUBS] [Verification: T]

4 Laboratory and Experiment Infrastructure

4.1 Baseline Design

The TVAC is located at TU Braunschweig and will be used for the LUXEX-experiments. Figure 1 shows the CAD model of the vacuum chamber and the different subsystems. The subsystems extraction and capturing will be mounted inside the TVAC (s. Figure 3). The other subsystems and the water storage will be placed outside the TVAC on racks next to it (s. Figure 1). Those subsystems are therefore accessible throughout the experiments.

Figure 2 shows a schematic of all the connections and valves connected to the TVAC, the subsystems extraction and capturing and the water storage. The extraction subsystem is accessible through a quick-access-door via a stainless-steel funnel and between the experiments through a second quick-access-door mounted to the lid of the crucible (s. Figure 4). The sample will be inserted through this funnel into the crucible (s. Figure 5). Therefore, it is needed to be able to flood and evacuate the crucible and the cold trap independently via the valves V_1 , V_2 and V_{ventCT} (s. Figure 2). Hence, the subsystems extraction and capturing will be accessible while the TVAC is cooled and evacuated.

The water storage will be split into two water tanks for simplification. Water storage 1 (s. Figure 6) is vacuum capable in order to show the functionality of the capturing and liquefaction against a vacuum environment. After one liquefaction-cycle the storage tank will be flooded to increase the pressure to ambient pressure and then the water will be pumped into the second storage tank. From there the water will enter the subsystem purification. Additionally, further contamination can be added to the water in this tank, which cannot be inserted in the TVAC because of safety reasons, e.g. HCL and H_2S .

All tubes inside the TVAC will be made out of stainless steel except for the tubes connected to the cold trap and the liquefaction. Those will be made out of copper in order to bend and heat them more easily. The pipes outside of the TVAC will be mainly corrugated tubes. Only the connections where liquid water will flow through are normal tubes.

In order to evacuate and flood the different parts of the subsystems extraction and capturing the valves shown in Figure 2 are needed. The valves also allow the individual connection of all parts with the TVAC as well as to one another. While connected to the TVAC any water vapor loss can be measured by a mass spectrometer. Table 1 displays different switching cases of the valves throughout the experiment.

The water vapor flow from the crucible to the cold trap will be controlled by the needle valve V_{CT} . All valves outside the TVAC will be electric-pneumatic except for the venting valves V_{ventCT} and V_{ventL} . Those two will be manual valves.

As the chamber will be evacuated and cooled with the already installed cooling system using liquid nitrogen while the subsystem capturing and extraction are still under ambient pressure, the valves V_1 - V_5 are necessary. The crucible and the cold trap will be cooled afterwards by filling liquid nitrogen through the funnel in the quick-access-door into the crucible.

Figure 4-1: Overview of the laboratory with the LUXEX-Components included. The subsystems extraction and capturing are located inside the chamber. On the right side of the chamber are the subsystems purification (orange), data acquisition and control (light blue) and water quality and condition monitoring (green) located.

Figure 4-2: Schematic of the pipes and valves between the subsystems extraction and capturing and the thermal vacuum chamber.

Table 4-1: Overview of the valve switching for different steps of the experiment. Green (O) signals an open valve and red a closed one.

Case	V _{VentCT}	V _{Slider}	V _L	V _{VentL}	V _{CT}	V ₁	V ₂	V ₃	V ₄	V ₅	V _{InSt}	V _{OutSt}	V _{Air}	V _{TMP}	V _{TVAC}
Pre-Cooling	O	O		O										O	
Sample Inserting	O													O	
Sample Drying I						O								O	
Sample Drying II							O							O	
Collecting Ice		O			O			O	O					O	
Liquefying Ice					O			O						O	
Filling Storage					O			O			O			O	
Drying Liquefaction I			O		O			O						O	
Drying Liquefaction II					O			O		O				O	
Emptying Storage		O			O			O				O	O	O	
Opening TVAC	O	O			O								O		O

Figure 4-3: Left image: Close-up on the inside of the TVAC. The grey container in the bottom middle is the crucible. In the top right corner is the cold trap located. The cooling rods inside the cold trapped are marked in violet and are visible through a window. Underneath the cold trap is the liquefaction located. Right image: Close-up on the crucible. On the lid are a feed through for electric wiring and a quick-access-door located. The lid of the quick-access-door is a window used for monitoring the inside of the crucible throughout the experiment.

Figure 4-4: Left image: The quick-access-door at the top of the TVAC is connected to the crucible. The sample material is inserted through this door in the crucible via a pipe with the help of a funnel. The yellow dot marks the position where the material will be inserted. Right image: Close-up on the first storage tank on the right side of the chamber. The storage tank is connected to the liquefaction via a copper pipe. The pressure inside the storage tank is measured. From this tank, water is pumped into the second storage tanks, which are part of the subsystem purification.

4.2 Options and Trade-offs

One Trade-off is the splitting of the water storage into two independent tanks. Combining storage tank 1 and 2 is possible but would be more complex and expensive. However, the splitting allows the insertion of extra contamination to the water in the second tank before the purification subsystem. This is needed as some contamination elements cannot be inserted in the TVAC because of safety reasons.

Further, the slider between the cold trap and the liquefaction limits the diameter of those two parts but is needed for the working principle.

4.3 Open Issues

One open issue is to avoid water vapor of going in the funnel and the evacuation pipe of the crucible instead of directly to the cold trap. A plug or a second slider and combining the funnel with the evacuation pipe of the crucible in one pipe might be solutions for that.

Further, the final configuration of the water quality and condition monitoring subsystem is unknown. This information is needed to provide enough space for the equipment next to the TVAC.

4.4 Preliminary Experiments

The fabrication of the ice simulant out of contaminated water will be tested and afterwards the thermal conductivity of the ice will be measured. Then experiments with the regolith and ice-regolith-mixtures concerning the gas extraction effectivity will be conducted. The thermal conductivities of both regolith and ice-regolith-mixtures will be measured, too.

5 Water Extraction Subsystem

In this chapter the overall design will be overviewed and discussed. This incorporates all components, processes and methods to achieve water extraction from ice within Lunar regolith. The next section describes the baseline design.

5.1 Baseline Design

The working principle of a crucible can be schematically overviewed by Figure 5-1. In here, a cylindrical volume is showed since it results in a more equally temperature distribution compared to a rectangular volume. Icy regolith is heated by heating rods and a heating foil, where ice within the regolith will be sublimated. Water vapour will flow towards a specific volume where it is collected before entering the intergration system. The integration system can be seen as assembly of connectors, i.e. tubes, pipes, pumps, measurement devices and electronics. In general, all components to ensure the flow towards the capturing system. In Figure 5-2 an overview is made in which all important components can be seen. This means that the pre-pump, filling tube, turbo pump, power lines and the inlet cold trap (or vapour outlet crucible) are referred as intergrated subsystems. On the lid, there will be the following openings:

- Channel for filling crucible with icy-regolith simulant and evacuating crucible with pre-pump.
- Channel leading to capturing subsystem.
- Viewing port with fast opening for (potentially) taking probes.
- The power feedthrough (D-Sub).

In this part, only the crucible is discussed and is therefore highlighted. Going back to Figure 5-1, the volume in which the water vapour will be collected can be seen as an extenct of filling the crucible. Therefore this volume represents a specific filling level of the icy regolith. Important to know is that the red volume contains the heating function. Suppose the heat flux is acting from a cylindrical rod, the length of this rod only reaches up till the end of the red volume. Later on, the collecting volume is determined based on optimal operating conditions, mass flow of water vapour and heat flow. Water should still be in constant vapour form leaving the crucible. This means that collection volume cannot be extended significantly since the ambient conditions will cool down the water to liquid or solid. Any parts integrated with the capturing system cannot be connected with the heat function. Inserting this volume means availability to integrate subsystems with the capturing system.

Figure 5-1: Schematic overview of processes inside the crucible; with volume $V = V_1$ (red) + V_2 (blue).

Figure 5-2: Overview of components within integrated systems; water extraction subsystem highlighted blue and water capturing subsystem highlighted red.

Figure 5-3 and Figure 5-4 show the geometry of above principle, the crucible. An overview is made for a design with five elements ($N = 5$) with radius R and height H . The heating rods with radius R_r and height H_r are distributed equally throughout the xy -plane the crucible, see Figure 5-3. Heat is applied on the wall of the crucible and heat is originated from the surface area of the rods. These boundary conditions can be seen in Figure 5-4. Surface to ambient radiation is possible from the outer surface of the crucible to the environment. Therefore, all outer boundaries of the sample volume are selected to radiate heat to the ambient. To simulate the thermal behavior of icy regolith, several models are used. In Table 5-1 below, the most important thermal properties are shown, together with the model. When creating new concepts and optimizing the actual design, thermal properties remained constant.

Table 5-1: Thermal properties of ice, dry regolith and icy regolith.

Sign	Name	Unit
$C_{p, dry}$	Specific heat capacity of dry regolith	J/K
k_{dry}	Thermal conductivity of dry regolith	W/m*K
$C_{p, i}$	Specific heat capacity of ice	J/K
k_i	Thermal conductivity of ice	W/m*K
$C_{p, icy}$	Specific heat capacity of icy regolith	J/K
k_{icy}	Thermal conductivity of icy regolith	W/m*K
φ	Porosity of icy regolith	-
F	Pore-filling fraction	-

Figure 5-3: Cross-sections with dimensions for $N = 5$; xy -plane (left); yz -plane (right) through dashed line.

Figure 5-4: Schematic 3D overview of the crucible; heat function for $N = 5$ within volume V_1 .

5.2 Options and Trade-offs

In this section the available options are mentioned. Before the concurrent-engineering study a trade-off is made for In-Situ Extraction (heated dome) and Excavated Extraction (crucible) (Kiewiet *et al.*, 2022). To elaborate shortly, In-Situ Extraction is achieved by the use of a heated dome while the use of a crucible defines the excavated method.

The crucible has much higher potential extraction rate, higher efficiency, and more flexible (less sensitive) to state of water on the moon and sample input. Moreover, exact configuration of rods will be decided by simulation and optimization (sublimation rate), see next section. The possibility to control groups of (or individually) rods for further optimized overall heat transfer is considered here. The power density, Q , is optimized where the performance of the cold trap is considered. Furthermore, additional means of manipulating the sample for increased heat and mass flow is considered.

5.2.1 Design optimization

Using COMSOL Multiphysics above design can be simulated, using only the number of heating rods, N , and the radius of the rod, R_r [m], as changing variables to create geometric similarity. For design optimization variables such as the power density Q [W], initial water content C_i are considered depended variables. In total there are four variables and two coefficients which are optimized during this stage. Eventually, the remaining variables can be changed in order to obtain the effect on water yield and extraction rate.

Table 5-2: Optimization of six variables and important values of parameters.

Variable		Unit	Optimization	Fixed value or relation
N	Number of rods	-	$[3 - M]$	
R_r	Radius of rod(s)	m	$[0.002 - 0.02]$	
Q	Power density	W	$[500 - 2500]$	
C_i	Initial water content	%	$[1-15]$	
T_i	Initial temperature	K		80
ε	Emissivity crucible	-		0.1
V_1	Volume with heat function	m^3		$\pi R^2 H$
V_2	Volume for collecting vapour	m^3		$\pi R^2 (0.27 - H)$
V	Total volume of the crucible	m^3		$V_1 + V_2$
H_r	Height of rod(s)	m		0.15
R	Radius of crucible	m		0.15
H	Height of crucible	m		0.15
a	Coefficient for distribution Q over rods, where $a + b = 1$	-	$0 < a < 1$	
b	Coefficient for distribution Q over wall, where $a + b = 1$	-	$0 < b < 1$	

5.2.2 Power Density – Q

For values of $Q < 500$ W the extraction takes over 6 days which is unacceptable. At this point, the limit of Q is therefore set to be a minimal of 500 Watts. Now Q can be changed in the range of 500 varying to 2500 Watts, depending on a reasonable heat flux. What’s more, temperature rise of the elements should be considered when implementing heat flux values. Temperature rise is controlled and explained later. To implement the power a heat flux is applied to the boundaries in Figure 5-4. As mentioned above, heat is originated from the rods and the crucible’s outer surface (wall). Two coefficients are implemented, a and b , in order to divide the power density over the wall and rods, see Table 5-3.

Table 5-3: Determining heat flux based on constant power density Q.

Variable		Unit	Relation
A_{rods}	Surface area of the heating elements, rods	m ²	$\pi NR_r^2 + 2\pi NR_r H_r$
A_{wall}	Surface area of the crucible's wall	m ²	$2\pi RH$
q_{rod}	Heat flux per heating element, rod	W/m ²	$a \frac{Q}{A_{rods}}$
q_{wall}	Heat flux on the wall	W/m ²	$b \frac{Q}{A_{wall}}$

5.2.3 Number of elements - N

At this stage, the number of elements define the heat flux per rod, since the power density Q is divided over N elements. As the heat flux increases, the extraction starts at an earlier stage.

5.2.4 Radii of elements - R_r

The radii of elements have a similar effect on the heat flux. Lowering the radius, and therefore the surface area, means an increase in heat flux per element. The extraction will therefore be deviating at different values of radii.

5.2.5 Initial content of water – C_i

The initial water content inside the regolith can be simulated within the range of 1% to 15%.

5.2.6 Coefficients – a, b

Adjusting coefficients, a and b will result in different heat fluxes for both the rods and the crucible's wall. There is a specific number when the heat flux for all rods equals the heat flux on the wall, which means:

$$q_{rod} = q_{wall}$$

This implies the following relation for coefficient b:

$$b = \frac{A_{wall}}{(A_{wall} + A_{rods})},$$

and coefficient a is defined as:

$$a = 1 - b.$$

5.2.7 Water Yield & Extraction Rate

Table 5-4 shows data input for three different concepts, since there are three different values for N. All concepts have equal mass stored of regolith in the crucible, named *m* in kg. As a result, the total mass of water does not have high priority. At this stage, the extraction rate is of great importance and therefore the extraction time. Coefficients a and b are defined in such a way that $q_{rod} = q_{wall}$ holds for each concept. Figure 5-5 shows the total water yield over time for six different cases. The extraction time is significantly lower for cases V and VI which are concepts with 19 heating elements. Based on this data, $N = 19$ is preferred over the other numbers. It takes over 600.000 seconds (≈ 167 hours) to reach 100% water yield.

The extraction rate in grams per hour is shown in Figure 5-6 for cases V and VI. An average extraction of 3.6 and 3.8 grams per hour is achieved for case V and VI, respectively. The highest peak is almost reaching 14 grams per hour of water extraction. There is a number of *N* for which the water yield is maximal at the smallest value of extraction time. To ensure an optimal flow the converting rate of the capturing system should match these values. When there is significant deviation between both systems, a pulsing heat source can be used, see for control methods in section 5.2.9 and open options in section 5.3.

When increasing *Q* to 1500 W for cases V and VI, the corresponding heat fluxes will be tripled when remaining every other variable constant. Now full extraction is achieved 220.000 seconds (≈ 61 hours). At this point, the only difference between case V and VI is the amount of water extracted since the radius of the rod deviates and therefore the volume of the icy regolith stored. There is no significant difference in extraction rate.

Table 5-4: Data input for 3 concepts based on several variables.

Input									
Case	N	R_r	Q	C_i	a	b	q_{rod}	q_{wall}	m [kg]
I	1	0.013	500	5	0.08	0.92	3238.6	3238.6	15.5
II	1	0.026	500	5	0.16	0.84	2967.2	2967.2	15.1
III	7	0.005	500	5	0.44	0.56	2858.6	2858.6	15.5
IV	7	0.01	500	5	0.33	0.67	2386.1	2386.1	15.1
V	19	0.003	500	5	0.28	0.72	2547.5	2547.5	15.5
VI	19	0.0061	500	5	0.44	0.56	1982.1	1982.1	15.1

Figure 5-5: Water yield in grams as function of time for six different cases.

Figure 5-6: Extraction rate in grams per hour for concept N = 19; cases V and VI.

5.2.8 Effect of remaining variables on water extraction

There are many variables in designing the water extraction subsystem, which is desirable. As a result of obtaining the effects of all variables a well-defined overview is conducted.

5.2.8.1 Initial temperature – T_i

The ambient temperature is initially set on 80 K. To see the effect on extraction, the temperature is now varying between 80 and 130 K. In reality, the temperature inside the TVAC will not be 80 K everywhere. The temperature will rise further away from the cold shroud.

5.2.8.2 Height of the element – H_r

The height of the element can be changed when there is sufficient reason for improving the extraction. For example, when implementing a rotating device attached to the heating elements the rods cannot be attached to the bottom of the crucible and thus not equal to $H_r = H$.

5.2.8.3 Thermal properties

When there are more accurate models for the specific regolith and icy regolith mixture, the thermal properties can be adjusted.

5.2.8.4 Total volume - V

Going back to section 6.1 Baseline Design, there is the collecting volume V_2 . Now that volume V_1 is obtained and the extraction rate is known, the pressure build-up can be implemented. In short, the pressure rise inside V_2 determines its value. Considering an optimal flow with respect to the converting rate of the capturing system there is a minor pressure rise. However, to minimize V_2 reevaluating of V_1 is necessary in order to maximize storage of regolith and therefore water yield. In short, the following steps need to be executed:

1. Determine pressure build-up based on current extraction rate and initial value V_1 .
2. Implement performance of capturing system.
3. Calculate water yield and extraction rate with the integrated volume V_2 . This means the crucible has now a total volume V .
4. Iteration of pressure build-up to minimize V_1 at an acceptable value of pressure rise.

5.2.9 Control

The temperature of the heated elements should not exceed maximum operating values of its material or a certain value for the regolith. Therefore, the heat flux applied to the elements and wall should be a function of time and the maximum temperature. Imagine at t_0 the temperature reaches $T = S T_{max}$. Here, S denotes a reasonable safety factor and coefficient $0 < c < 1$ to ensure decrease of heat flux and therefore preventing reaching T_{max} .

Table 5-5: Controlling temperature rise of regolith and/or materials used.

Control Input		
q	T	t
$q = q_0$	$T < S T_{max}$	$t < t_0$
$q = \frac{q_0}{c}$	$T > S T_{max}$	$t > t_0$

5.3 Open Issues

There are several issues which need to be solved. First of all, when looking at Figure 5-2, connecting the power lines for heating needs to be considered.

Fixing the heating elements inside the crucible is still unknown. It depends on whether there is significant reason to implement rotating heating elements or a rotating device with static elements. This will be further considered.

In terms of controlling, the temperature sensors need to be located and actuators need to be applied. Note that the data in section 195.2.7 is still prior to the actual data there is today.

6 Water Capturing Subsystem

The most important criteria of the water capturing subsystem is reliably capturing as much water as possible during the test, since the captured water will be further processed and investigated in later steps of the project. It is also relevant to design a system that reflects a future design which could be used on the Moon, but out of practicality there might be a discrepancy between the actual design and the most optimal design. Other important criteria are its complexity, lifetime, TRL, system mass, and efficiency. Its functionality is defined as follows.

The capture subsystem shall:

- Capture the water vapour,
- Induce a flow towards the capturing subsystem,
- Collect the water,
- Liquefy the water.

The two main methods considered for the LUXWEX project are:

- Cold trap, the water vapour is deposited as ice on a cold surface.
- Condenser, the water vapour is condensed on a cold surface.
- Difference between the two is the phase, the temperature and pressure at which it occurs.

6.1 Baseline Design

This section describes the preliminary design as the result of the Concurrent-Engineering study. As described in the trade-off in section, the decision was in favour of a cold trap with external liquefaction.

A cold trap is a cold surface to which the water vapour coming from the crucible can deposit onto as a solid, after which it can be considered captured and secured.

A needle valve between the cold trap chamber and the vacuum chamber controls the vapour flow towards the actual cold trap itself and prevents the pressure rising too much should that happen. A slider separates the cold trap chamber from the liquefaction chamber. In Figure 5-2 an overview of the entire experiment design is presented, and in Figure 6-2 the process is described in more detail. In Figure 6-1 a preliminary CAD drawing of the relevant systems is presented. In the crucible, the water vapour has a temperature of over 273K after heating the regolith. This refers to a saturation pressure of 470 Pa which is then also present then in the cold trap and liquefaction. For more details regarding the valves and infrastructure see chapter 4.

Present volatiles in the icy-regolith sample are water ice, methanol, ethanol, CO₂. The cold trap has to withstand these volatiles and is designed in such a way, that these volatiles are not deposited on the cold fingers. For more regarding the composition and amounts of the icy-regolith sample and its volatiles see chapter 10.

The design was driven by volume constraints of the chamber and size of the slider which separates the cold trap and the liquefaction.

The goals of this baseline design were as follows:

1. As much cold trap area as possible for maximal ice mass and thus water vapour capturing.
2. Long residence time of the vapour for lower losses leading to a higher efficiency.
3. High liquefaction volume to lower the need for melting cycles for a higher total collection rate.

6.1.1 Conversion of Cooling Power to liquid Nitrogen

Liquid nitrogen is sufficiently available and the flow rate is high enough to realize a cooling power in the order of around 1kW. The cold fingers are conductively connected to a liquid nitrogen inlet for the cold shroud of the chamber leading to a high possible cooling power.

6.1.2 Cooling surface

The cooling surface needs to be maximized to minimize losses of vapour through the needle valve. In the present design, the surface is as high as possible with cylindrical cold fingers while maintain a sufficient radius for heat conduction. The cooling surface is also dependent on the sublimation rate of the crucible and is going to be adapted to it with simulations via COMSOL Multiphysics.

Figure 6-1: Preliminary CAD-drawing of the cold trap and liquefaction.

Figure 6-2: Process scheme of the cold trap and liquefaction. All values are subject to change.

As soon as water vapour travels from the crucible to the cold trap, the collection process starts, as can be seen in Figure 5-1. The water vapour is deposited on several “cold fingers”. As the ice deposits on the cold trap, the efficiency is reduced the thicker the ice layer is. After a certain point, the delamination is started to free the cold trap. The cold fingers can be seen through a window with a camera. This delamination is most likely done via an electrically induced vibration, for more see chapter 6.2. The delaminated ice falls down through the slider into the liquefaction container. It has to be noted, that the cold trap is cylindrical and has the same diameter as the circular slider to facilitate falling of the ice. The deposition of ice and delamination are repeated until the liquefaction container is full of ice.

Consequently, the slider is closed so that the liquefaction is sealed and has its own environment as can be seen in t=2 of Figure 6-2. Heat is applied to the ice in the liquefaction leading to a pressure and temperature rise so that liquid water can exist. Meanwhile, more ice can be collected on the cold fingers. If the liquefaction process takes longer than the re-sublimation on the cold fingers, the heating in the crucible may be adapted to reduce the water vapour flow and thus minimize losses to the TVAC.

When all the water is liquified, it can flow to the storage tank next to the TVAC. This is repeated, until the storage tank is full and a batch of water is present (t=3). Lastly, the water flows to the tank of the purification system meanwhile the liquefaction is evacuated so that it can store ice again.

6.1.3 Ice Collection Rate

The data of a thesis (Jurado, 2021) allowed an initial extrapolation of the collection rate on a cold surface. The ice density reported here has a maximum of 92 kg/m³ which has a strong influence on the result. By extrapolation, within 8 hours, equal to a normal working day, 1.1 kg of ice could be collected, as can be seen in Table 6-1. This is of course a rough estimation based on one data point. The delamination and usage of the slider are not considered yet. This collection rate shall be in line with the desired amount of water for the purification system, which is around 500 ml.

Table 6-1: Extrapolation of the collection rate based on Jurado 2021’s thesis (Green: Input value for the calculation).

Description	Value	Unit
Maximum ice thickness	4	mm
Number of rods	13	
Height of a rod	200	mm
Radius of a rod	5	mm
Volume of a rod	15708	mm ³
Volume of a rod + ice	50893	mm ³
Volume of the ice per rod	35185	mm ³
Total volume for all rods	457415	mm ³
Mass (g) with 92 $\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$	42.1	g
Surface of an empty rod	6283	mm ³
Surface total # rods	81681	mm ³
Jurado 2021 Surface	1600	mm ³
Ratio Total A to Jurado A	51.1	$\frac{\text{mm}^3}{\text{mm}^3}$
Collection Rate Jurado	0,00076	$\frac{\text{g}}{\text{s}}$
Extrapolation Collection Rate	0,03900	$\frac{\text{g}}{\text{s}}$
Time required for a gram of ice	25.6	s
Available time per day (8h)	28800	s
Collected water w/o delamination	1123.1	g

6.2 Options and Trade-offs

In Figure 6-3, a schematic phase diagram of water and possible paths of the extracted water are shown. First, the water is in solid state at a very low temperature and pressure in the bottom left corner. Then, heat is applied and it sublimates during extraction (1). After that, it is either directly liquified (3), which is can be realized with a condenser, or the vapour is deposited as ice on a cold trap (2a) and then liquified with another process (2b).

Figure 6-3: Water phase diagram. Paths are schematic; temperature and pressure regions are not exact.

One of the main differences between these two processes, compare the arrows 3, 2a and 2b in Figure 6-3, is the additional phase change to ice when using a cold trap. This has strong influence on the temperature and pressure requirements needed as discussed further in section 6.2.4 Trade-Off. For purification of the sample, water in liquid state is needed. This requires a significant pressure change above 615Pa, either after the deposition as ice on the cold trap (2b) or before the condenser (3).

In Figure 6-4, possible options for the capturing of the water vapour are shown in a DoT:

Figure 6-4: Overview of possible options for the capturing subsystem.

The vapour could either be captured in an icy or liquid state. For both possibilities, the vapour flow needs to be induced and guided somehow, as discussed in 6.2.3.

For the first option, the ice needs to be somehow liquefied, either directly in the cold trap itself, described as “integrated liquefaction”, or in an “external liquefaction”, whereas the ice is moved to another environment and then liquified there. The integrated liquefaction has the drawback of stopping the collection for a longer time while the environment of the cold trap is then heated and pressurized. Also, after a liquefaction process, it needs to be cooled again. These factors most likely are going to have a negative impact on the collection rate and energy consumption.

With the external liquefaction, the cold trap operates continuously, with only some breaks for the delamination of the ice. Another requirement for better continuity is that the external liquefaction has the same rate of liquefaction in terms of mass as the cold trap’s collection rate. A scheme for a cold trap with an external liquefaction can be seen in Figure 6-5. On the moon, the liquefaction subsystem could be separated from the cold trap system, meaning ice would be intermediately stored first.

Besides, for the cold trap, a delamination mechanism for the ice from the cold surface is needed. Some options for this are explored in section 6.2.1. Furthermore, cold traps can be realized only with valves and not with a pump or piston, leading to a lower complexity than the condenser.

The options for capturing in liquid state can be classified in continuous and non-continuous operations. For continuity, a constant flow of water vapour to the condensing surface at sufficient pressure and temperatures above the triple point is needed. This could be realized with a pump between the extraction subsystem and the capturing subsystem, if the liquid phase is not allowed in the extraction subsystem. A high pressure in the crucible is unwanted since the water should only be in solid or gas state during extraction. Such a system is shown in Figure 6-6.

Still, the extraction subsystem and condenser could be directly connected and with sufficient heating the pressure would most likely rise sufficiently. Furthermore, all surfaces must be kept over 0°C to prevent unwanted deposition or condensation. This could be an option for continuously condensing without a pump with the drawback of a high heating requirement.

Lastly, the water vapour could be collected in the condenser volume which is temporarily sealed off from the extraction subsystem. After that, the pressure needs to be risen, e.g. thermally or via volume reduction possibly realized with a piston. This is an example for capturing in liquid state with non-continuous operations.

In the next two subsections, the cold plate, meaning capturing the vapour as ice, and the condenser, are further explored.

6.2.1 Capturing in solid form

If the vapour shall be captured in an icy state, in principle, the pressure and temperature from the crucible can be used. In this scenario, liquid water occurs after the capturing in a solid state. The gathered ice needs to be in an environment where liquid water can exist. Whether this change in pressure and temperature takes places directly in the capturing system (internal liquefaction) or whether the ice is detached from the capturing system and processed in another location (external liquefaction) needs to be decided. This decision has high influence on the pressure barrier as well.

One advantage is that the Δp and ΔT between the Lunar environment and the inside of the cold trap is smaller compared with the liquid phase, meaning less insulation is needed and the losses are lower. Research conducted by Holquist *et al.* (2021) presents more information about this too, as well a possible synergy between capturing and purification.

Furthermore, no solidification of the water vapour at the walls of the tube to the CS and the surrounding walls of the cold plate shall occur. Hence, the temperature of the walls must be controlled.

Figure 6-5: Schematic for a cold trap with external liquefaction.

For the capturing as a solid, a shake-off or detaching mechanism is needed. The following options regarding detachment could be:

1. Detachment via electricity. The current induces a magnetic field and leads to shaking/vibration of the rods or cold fingers.
2. Detachment induced by thin heating foil around or on the cold surfaces.
3. Detachment performed manually.

Continuous operations with a single cold plate seem possible, since the delamination process of Jurado (2021) took about 15 mins. It is questionable whether the delamination process is the same if the cold plate is significantly bigger.

6.2.2 Capturing in liquid form

Figure 6-6: Schematic of a condenser.

Condensation is transferring from the gas phase to the liquid phase. The process must take place in the liquid region in the water phase diagram, meaning above the triple point (273.16K & 611.66Pa). Consequently, the Δp and ΔT to the TVAC or Lunar environment is larger compared to capturing in solid form (with the cold trap). This could lead to higher losses and has implications on complexity of the insulation and heating. However, since liquid water is the desired end-product of the capturing system, an extra liquefaction step is not needed.

This paragraph describes some interesting findings from Liu *et al.* (2023). The usage of a guiding tube, as seen in Figure 6-7, to the cold surface strongly enhanced collection efficiency. The efficiency also strongly decreases off the vapour density is too low. A continuous droplet condensation is needed. Also, his team found

out that the discharge of the residual water vapour to induce the flow to the TVAC may increase pressure to around orders of magnitude of 1000Pa in the vacuum chamber.

Figure 6-7: Photos of a water condenser. Courtesy of Liu *et al.* (2023).

Some of the process parameters extracted from Liu 2023 are shown in the table below:

Table 6-2: Process parameters of the condenser extracted from Liu *et al.* (2023).

Description	Value	Unit
Range of liquid water flow rates	≈ 6-150	$\frac{\text{ml}}{\text{h}} = \frac{\text{g}}{\text{h}}$
Condensed water	16-51	g
Energy input	308-607	Wh
Energy efficiency	6-37.9	$\frac{\text{Wh}}{\text{g}}$
Temperature of the vapour after extraction	≈100	°C
Operating temperature of vapour in the condenser (p.397 Liu2023)	3-7	°C
Temperature of the condensing surface (p.397 Liu2023)	0-5	°C
Operating pressure	1, decreasing	bar
Coolant Temperature	-1	°C

For the experiment, a pilot-scale facility in a vacuum-chamber with 1.6m in height and a diameter of 0.6m was utilized. A full loop system from drilling, excavation, heating, vapour collection and condensation to liquid was constructed. The pressure drops during operation, but the exact pressure region has not been recorded.

Cooling of the condenser is realised by a chiller. Basically, it consists of a metallic base part with conical shape and an even, transparent cover made of PMMA. In the base part, there are several openings, e.g. for the in- and outlet, respectively. The surface for condensing is hydrophilic.

6.2.3 Options to induce a water vapour flow from the crucible to the capturing system

After the water vapour has been gassed out, it needs to flow towards the capturing sub system. This could be realized with a pressure difference. The pressure inside the crucible and capturing subsystem is higher than in the TVAC. This could be used for a driving force, controlled by (solenoid) valves or a needle valve. At least valves are a possibility. Using a pump to induce the flow is an option as well, most likely in combination for the needed pressure rise for a condenser.

6.2.4 Trade-Off

For the graphical Trade-Off Table, the score classifications are defined as the following:

Excellent	Dark green
Good	Green
Correctable deficiencies	Yellow
Unacceptable	Red
Unanalysed	White

In the first column, the requirement is stated. In the 2nd and 3rd column, they are qualitatively judged via colours for the respective method.

Table 6-3: Graphical Trade-Off Table.

Criterion	Capturing as ice (cold plate)	Capturing as liquid (condenser)
Phase Change Energy needed	Slightly higher (about 20%)	Lowest need, since it is only a phase change with one phase
Energy for the System Environment needed	"Only" freezing at the walls has to be prevented. Pressure & temperature difference to TVAC is lower	Liquid region of water has higher requirements for the temperature and pressure: >>600 Pa, >0°C vs. TVAC
		=> more insulation, pressurization and heating needed, hence more losses
		Possibly vacuum Isolation needed for condenser (around 4kw extra cooling)
		Heating most likely not feasible
Complexity of the design	Mechanism/Pressurization for the proceeding with the ice capturing needed	Pump needed (most likely) & condensation design is more complex & effective heating method for the gas is needed
TRL/Reliability	More literature and experiments have been found	
Simulation	Most likely easier, especially if only a plate	Fluid water flow included
Liquefaction	Heating of the ice in a closed environment can lead to liquid water. Heat transfer is possible via conduction to the ice, that's why this environment needs less insulation to the TVAC (and no vacuum insulation with extra pump)	Gas needs to be pressurized and then heated or cooled.
Purification	No clear advantage, although proven possible by Holquist 2021.	No clear advantage
Capturing Capability	Depend on the surface/post-processing	Continuous flow

The main reason for the decision of capturing as a solid, meaning cold trapping, was less complexity, since no means to rise the pressure between the crucible and the capturing system is needed. The condenser needs pumps and valves with pressure control to function efficiently and optimally. Besides, the insulation of a condenser is more complex since increasing or decreasing the enthalpy of a vapour is more difficult. Another reason was that the cold trap makes better use of the native environment on the moon. Also, less heat and control schemes are required to achieve the desired temperature and pressure ranges. In future systems with cold trapping, the liquefaction might not occur directly after the capturing, so the intermediate storage could be in icy state. This reduces the storage complexity and favours the design with a cold trap.

6.3 Open Issues

In this section, a list of open issues and further work is presented.

1. Dust and contaminants of the regolith sample are introduced into the whole subsystem. The influence on moving parts and a possible built-up as well as the necessity of countermeasures need to be investigated.
2. The liquefaction has two states in the current baseline design: Storing the ice at a temperature only slightly higher than the cold trap temperature or liquify the water at circa 298K. This imposes high demands on the insulation, cooling and heating capability as well as on the sealing to the cold fingers and the pipes for venting and the liquid water.
3. Presently, the cold fingers are thermally connected to the cold shroud of the TVAC without a mean of temperature control. This is desired for a pre-purification as is done in Holquist *et al.* (2021) did since the current temperature is far away from the operational envelope described in that research. For example, a heat pipe for the thermal connection should be designed in such a way, that the temperature of the cold fingers is maintained at the operational envelope while ensuring the release of the phase change enthalpy.
4. The slider could be blocked, e.g. via ice, dust or contaminants built-up or ice which falls down from the cold fingers. The data sheet of the slider and the possibility of these events needs to be checked further.
5. After a successful detachment of the water ice from the cold fingers, the ice falls into the liquefaction due to gravity. A wedging of the ice in the cold fingers has to be prevented and as mentioned above, the ice shall not block the slider. The cold finger region could be monitored with the already present camera there. Besides, the gravity is lower on the moon which would lead to less falling forces.
6. Since the system should run as autonomous as possible, the filling state of the liquefaction needs to be reported to the control system. This could be realized with light barriers or a camera. The closing of the slider and closing of the connecting valves needs to be controlled for the liquefaction process. Furthermore, the end of the liquefaction process needs to be marked as well. This could be implemented via pressure monitoring.
7. The temperature gradient over the slider during the liquefaction is very high. The losses of heat and its compensation as well as further implication on the slider, e.g. the mechanics and sealings, has to be checked. First starting point is the data sheet of the slider.
8. No reliable data for the water ice density has been found. This value is needed to estimate how much water can be gained during a single liquefaction. If the density is too low, it has strong negative influence on the overall water collection rate.
9. To determine the ice built-up on the cold fingers, especially the rate and efficiency, ratio of mass captured to mass evaporated, an experiment will be conducted.
10. The collection rate needs to be tailored to the evaporation rate in the crucible. The data from the pre-experiment and simulations in COMSOL are going to be used.
11. The control scheme of the needle valve to maintain a pressure below 600Pa and to induce flow towards the capturing subsystem needs to be designed and implemented. The losses to the TVAC need to be minimized. The lower vapour mass flow at the beginning and ending of an extraction must be handled. Possibly, the needle valve is completely closed at the beginning for reaching a minimum operating pressure.
12. The sensor placement, especially temperature sensors, need to be determined. The pressure sensors are placed outside the TVAC and their place has been more or less been fixed during the CE-Study by the Infrastructure-team.
13. The first water vapour from the crucible needs to be detected. This could be done via pressure monitoring.
14. The cold fingers geometry could be optimized.
15. The wiring of heaters, camera(s), eventual light barriers, engine of the slider and temperature sensors inside the TVAC needs to be done.

7 Water Purification and Storage

Water Purification and Storage Subsystem (WPS) shall treat raw water coming from water extraction and capturing subsystem. Composition of raw water is based on Holquist *et al.* (2021) as shown in Table 7-1 – Raw Water volatiles contaminants.

Table 7-1 – Raw Water volatiles contaminants

Component	Best After Trap	Case Cold	Worst After Trap	Case Cold
	[mg/L]		[mg/L]	
Ammonia	1.67E-01		8.79E-01	
Methanol	3.74E-02		2.66E+00	
Sulphur dioxide	2.49E-03		7.83E-02	
Hydrogen sulphide	9.47E-04		4.17E-03	
Carbon dioxide	7.34E-04		7.34E-03	
Ethylene	1.56E-04		9.35E-04	
Hydrogen	1.46E-04		3.03E-04	
Carbon Monoxide	3.11E-05		4.67E-04	
Methane	2.68E-06		2.68E-05	

Other inorganic contaminants coming from contact with dust are present as per Table 7-2 – Raw Water inorganic contaminants.

Table 7-2 – Raw Water inorganic contaminants

Component		Concentration [mg/L]
Silicon	Si	0.009
Aluminium	Al	0.007
Calcium	Ca	0.02
Iron	Fe	<0.0004
Titanium	Ti	<0.00001
Magnesium	Mg	0.0032
Sulphur	S	0.00015
Manganese	Mn	0.00015
Potassium	K	0.003

In the raw water simulant that is used to test the subsystem, for safety reason, only ammonia, methanol, sulfur dioxide, hydrogen sulfide, carbon dioxide and ethylene are present. In the next paragraphs contaminants are divided into categories:

- Particulate: 500 mg/L of dust simulant $d < 2 \mu\text{m}$ is present in raw water simulant
- Organics: the most critical for removal is methanol
- Inorganics: the most critical for removal is ammonia.

7.1 Baseline Design

Raw water coming from extraction and capturing subsystem arrives to water purification subsystem. The WPS shall be able to produce technical water and potable water as per LUXWEX-LSG-WP2.1-D2.1-System Requirements Document_v1.0.

WPS works in batch mode with 10 ml/min flowrate.

Water purification process as described below is shown in the P&ID in Figure 7-1.

The subsystem breadboard tanks (T001, T002 and T003) are glass bottles connected to the other units. Glass bottles are chosen because of the versatility, the compatibility with the water contaminants, the easiness in cleaning and the compatibility with scales (S001 and S002) as level sensors. Furthermore, glass allows visual monitoring during tests. In a future flight-like model tanks will be AISI 316/316L stainless steel.

Raw water coming from extraction and capturing subsystem is stocked in tank T001. T001 can be filled with a second stream trough V001 in case of need or in test configuration when WPS is not connected to WECS. Water level in T001 is controlled using a scale (S001). A sampling port is placed after each technology in order to allow sample collecting and testing. At first water flows through the microfiltration unit (F001) constituted by a microfiltration membrane with pores 0.45 μm TBC that removes dust particulate. A differential pressure sensor ($\Delta P01$) indicates when the pressure drop is too high and the filter needs to be substituted. A water quality monitoring unit from Wroclaw University of Science and Technology can be connected between microfiltration and reverse osmosis unit. Water flows through a reverse osmosis membrane. The concentrate is recirculated to the system until the pressure given by the pump is not able to provide the set permeate flowrate. At this point V002 is opens and the concentrate is discharged in T002. After RO unit water passes across the activated carbon unit (AC001). Activated carbon unit is regenerated with a counter current flow of team coming from clean water tank. The regeneration process happens after a determinate amount of purification cycles and not simultaneously to the water purification process. The last purification unit is an ion exchange resins unit (R001). Before entering in the final clean water storage tank (T003), water passes through quality and condition monitoring subsystems respectively under Wroclaw University of Science and Technology and Scanway responsibility. Clean water tank T003 water level is monitored using a scale as T001. Conductivity probes are placed at the beginning of the process, after RO and in Wroclaw university unit after ion exchange resins to monitor the reliability of the process and usage of consumables.

The aim and the functioning of each technology is described in chapter 7.2.1.

Figure 7-1: Water Purification and Storage Subsystem preliminary P&ID

A preliminary CAD drawing of WPS is shown in Figure 7-2. In Figure 7-3 the maximum envelope expected for WPS is highlighted.

Figure 7-2: Water Purification and Storage Subsystem preliminary CAD drawing with open points.

Figure 7-3: Water Purification and Storage Subsystem preliminary CAD drawing with main envelope.

Figure 7-4 shows the interfaces (fluidic, mechanical and electrical) of WPS.

- 1, fluidic interface within WECS and T001: ¼" Swagelok female fitting (SS)
- 2, fluidic interface within WPS and Wrocław University water quality monitoring unit: ¼" CPC QD female fitting (Acetate)
- 3, fluidic interface within Wrocław University water quality monitoring unit and WPS: ¼" CPC QD male fitting (Acetate)
- 4, fluidic interface within WPS and Scanway water quality monitoring unit: ¼" CPC QD female fitting (Acetate)
- 5, fluidic interface within Wrocław University water quality monitoring unit and WPS: ¼" CPC QD male fitting (Acetate)

- 6, Power and data interface: D38999 circular female fitting
- 7,8, electrical connection of S001 and S002 to 220VAC: 10A plug

Figure 7-4: Water Purification and Storage Subsystem external interface definition status.

7.2 Options and Trade-offs

A trade-off is made in order to identify and choose the technologies already described in the paragraph above.

As first step, a revision of the state of the art is done and technologies available for the removal of contaminants are identified and divided into categories based on the removed contaminant (Table 7-3: List of the available technologies).

Table 7-3: List of the available technologies.

Contaminant	Removal Technology
Particulate	Microfiltration
	Cyclonic separation
	Sedimentation
	Coagulation + Flocculation + Sedimentation
Organics	Activated Carbon
	Photocatalytic oxidation
	Catalytic Oxidation
	Steam/air Stripping
Inorganics	Ion exchange Resins
	Electrodialysis
	Reverse Osmosis
	Membrane distillation
	Nanofiltration
	Nafion Membrane Stripping

7.2.1 Technologies overview

7.2.1.1 Microfiltration

Particulate of regolith in the water coming from extraction is present. It is reasonably considered that particles of $d < 1 \mu\text{m}$ needs to be removed. Microfiltration is a physical process able to remove particles of $d > 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ depending on the pore size of the membrane. It is the easiest and commonly used technology for particulate removal, but it clogs increasing pressure drops in the system and needs to be substituted producing consumables. (Huisman, 2000)

7.2.1.2 Cyclonic separation

Cyclonic separation uses the centrifugal force to separate solid particulate from water. Cyclonic separation for such low flowrates can be performed in mini-hydrocyclones (Yang *et al.*, 2013). It is a laboratory technology designed for separating particles with $d > 3 \mu\text{m}$ from water with efficiency $> 85\%$. Cyclonic separation does not use consumables.

7.2.1.3 Sedimentation

Sedimentation is the process normally used in water treatment plants. It works according to Stokes law only in laminar regime. For particles of $d < 1 \mu\text{m}$, the settling velocity is too slow and particulate doesn't sediment. Sedimentation does not use consumables.

7.2.1.4 Coagulation + Flocculation + Sedimentation

Coagulation and flocculation are processes used to separate suspended particles, that are too small for sedimentation, in water. In coagulation, chemicals are added to water to neutralize charges of the particles, in this way they tend to agglomerate. Flocculation is a gentle mixing process aimed to increase the diameter of the particles. After those processes' sedimentation can happen. This process requires continuous addition of consumables.

7.2.1.5 Activated Carbon

Activated Carbon is normally used for organics removal from water. It works through the process of adsorption (Al-Dawery, 2016). Because of the low affinity of methanol, which is one of the major contaminants present in WPS inlet water, with activated carbon, a great amount of carbon would be needed to treat the water stream. It is possible to regenerate activated carbon using counter-current steam, lowering consumables and making AC competitive in the trade-off.

7.2.1.6 Photocatalytic oxidation

Organic substances can be oxidized in a photocatalytic reactor. In photocatalysis UV irradiation of a semiconductor catalyst excites electrons from the valence to the conduction band, leaving holes behind. These electron-hole pairs migrate to the surface where they initiate redox reactions with organics adsorbed on the Titania-based catalyst. (Nelson *et al.*, 2007)

7.2.1.7 Catalytic oxidation

Oxidation of organics happens over noble metal and metal oxide catalyst (e.g. Pt, TiO_2 ...). Operating parameters such as inlet concentration, residence time and inlet temperature, influence the organics conversion (van de Beld *et al.*, 1994). Heat is needed to increase feed temperature to have an efficient conversion.

7.2.1.8 Steam or Air stripping

Stripping using steam or air is used for removing organics and part of inorganics (Ammonia) from wastewaters (Boul *et al.*, 2010). Methanol removal efficiency of air/steam stripping is high. Water and air/steam pass counter-current in a stripping column and contaminants transfer from water to air/steam according to Henry's Law.

7.2.1.9 Ion exchange resins

Ion exchange resins are resins porous microbeads that trap ions and release different ions. In water purification, ion exchange resins are used to remove unwanted ions from solution replacing with other ions. Usually in water treatment is used for final polishing. Resins exhaust after a designed time and need to be regenerated or substituted.

7.2.1.10 Electrodialysis

Electrodialysis uses the principle of ion exchange (Anthony *et al.*, 2013). An electrodialysis stack contains alternating cation and anion exchange membranes between two electrodes, with fluid-containing channels between each. The contaminated feed solution and the initially clean waste solution passes through the chamber and direct current is applied across the electrodes. Anionic and cationic contaminants diffuse across the membranes and become trapped in the waste solution. The water recovery is low (c.a. 5%) because of the high amount of clean water needed as waste solution.

7.2.1.11 Reverse osmosis

Reverse osmosis is a process that uses a partially permeable membrane. RO membranes do not allow large molecules (e.g. ammonia and inorganic salts) to pass through the pores of the membrane while smaller molecules, as water, can pass to the permeate side. RO works with higher pressures because the applied pressure needs to overcome the osmotic pressure. This implies high energy consumptions.

7.2.1.12 Membrane distillation

Membrane distillation is a separation process based on temperature gradient. The temperature gradient on the membrane results in a vapor pressure difference. Water vapor is selectively transported from the feed side of the membrane to the permeate side in a water vapor partial pressure difference driven process. No consumables are used for this process.

7.2.1.13 Nanofiltration

Nanofiltration is a physical process able remove ammonia and inorganic salts with good efficiency (98% ca.) from water using less energy compared to Reverse Osmosis because it can operate at lower pressure (Hurtado and Cancino-Madariaga, 2014). Nanofiltration membranes have pore sizes from 1-10 nm and retain ammonia. The concentrate stream can be recirculated to increase water recovery.

7.2.1.14 Nafion membrane stripping

Membrane distillation using Nafion membrane and a sulphuric acid stripping solution is an energetically favourable process for ammonia removal (Guo *et al.*, 2019). Ammonia passes through Nafion hydrophobic membrane and thanks to sulphuric acid in the permeate solution becomes ammonium. Sulphuric acid stripping solution is continuously needed in the process.

7.2.2 Evaluation criteria and relative weight

Criteria to evaluate the performance and advantages of the different technologies are established. A comparison within each criterion is done in order to define the relative weight of the votes that will be given to the criteria (Table 7-4: Criteria relative weight table).

Table 7-4: Criteria relative weight table.

Criteria	Water recovery	Process Wastes	Consumables	TRL	Sum	Relative Weight
Water recovery	1	1	1	0	3	0.30
Process Wastes	0	1	0	0	1	0.10
Consumables	0	1	1	0	2	0.20
TRL	1	1	1	1	4	0.40

7.2.3 First technologies screening

For each technology it is evaluated if the removal efficiency allows to reach the required value of the contaminants in output water (OK) or not (KO).

If a technology is rates as KO, the combination with other technologies is evaluated.

7.2.4 Vote assignment and second technologies screening

Votes are assigned to each technology for each criterion depending on ranges (Table 7-5: Votes assignment table).

Table 7-5: Votes assignment table.

	Water recovery	Process wastes	Consumables
1	<90%	Continuous PW	Continuous
2	91<WR<94 %	High volume PW	High weight
3	95<WR<96 %	Low volume PW	Low weight
4	97<WR<98%	once in process life	once in process life
5	99<WR<100%	No PW	No consumables

For each category of contaminants, the weighted sum of the votes is compared and technologies with lower grades are discarded.

Table 7-6: Particulate removal technologies rating.

Technology	Water Recovery	Process Wastes	Consumables	TRL	Weighted Sum
Microfiltration (MF)	5	3	3	4	4.0
Cyclonic separation + MF	4.5	3	4	2	3.3
Sedimentation + MF	2	1	4	1	2.0
Coagulation + Flocculation + Sedimentation + MF	2	1	1	1	1.5

Table 7-6 shows that sedimentation + MF and coagulation + flocculation + sedimentation + MF are not favourable for particulate removal.

Table 7-7: Organics removal technologies rating.

Technology	Water Recovery	Process Wastes	Consumables	TRL	Weighted Sum
Activated carbon	5	2	2	5	4.1
Photocatalytic oxidation	5	5	2	2	3.2
Catalytic oxidation	5	5	2	3	3.6
Steam stripping	4	5	4	3	3.7
Air stripping	4	5	3.5	3	3.6

From Table 7-7 it is possible to state that all the listed technologies for organics removal except for photocatalytic oxidation are comparable.

Table 7-8: Inorganics removal technologies rating.

Technology	Water Recovery	Process Wastes	Consumables	TRL	Weighted Sum
Ion exchange resins	5	2	2	5	4.1
Electrodialysis	1	1	1	1	1.0
Reverse osmosis	4	3	5	4	4.1
Membrane distillation	5	3	5	3	4.0
Nanofiltration	4	3	5	4	4.1
Nafion membrane stripping	5	1	1	2	2.6

Table 7-8 highlights that electrodialysis and Nafion membrane stripping have much lower grades than the other technologies considered for inorganics removal.

7.2.5 Final Trade-off table

Considering the screening of technologies described above, the final trade off table is identified.

Table 7-9: Final trade-off table.

	Technology	Water Recovery	Process Wastes	Consumables	TRL	Weighted Sum
Particulate	Microfiltration (MF)	5	3	3	4	4.0
	Cyclonic separation + MF	4.5	3	4	2	3.3
Organics	Activated carbon	5	2	2	5	4.1
	Catalytic oxidation	5	5	2	3	3.6
	Steam stripping	4	5	4	3	3.7
	Air stripping	4	5	3.5	3	3.6

Inorganics	Ion exchange resins	5	2	2	5	4.1
	Reverse osmosis	4	3	5	4	4.1
	Membrane distillation	5	3	5	3	4.0
	Nanofiltration	4	3	5	4	4.1

7.2.6 Preliminary baseline configuration and Assumptions

Some assumptions are made to identify the technology for the removal of each class of contaminant that are presented in the preliminary configuration.

For particulate removal, if particles $d > 2 \mu\text{m}$ are present in raw water, cyclonic separation before microfiltration is needed to lower the clogging of the microfiltration membrane. As in raw water only particles of $d < 2 \mu\text{m}$ are present, cyclonic separation is not needed and only microfiltration is used.

For organics removal, focusing on methanol, activated carbons are chosen because of higher TRL and removal efficiency. To reduce the consumables, activated carbons are regenerated using steam.

Reverse osmosis for inorganics removal is chosen because of the high removal efficiency of all the present species, especially for ammonia. Ion exchange resins are used for final polishing.

The baseline configuration is identified as in Table 7-10: Baseline configuration and is described in chapter 8.1.

Table 7-10: Baseline configuration.

	Technology	Water Recovery	Process Wastes	Consumables	TRL	Weighted Sum
Particulate	Microfiltration (MF)	5	3	3	4	4.0
Inorganics	Reverse Osmosis	4	3	5	4	4.1
Organics	Activated carbon	5	2	2	5	4.1
Polishing	Ion Exchange Resins	5	2	2	5	4.1

7.3 Open Issues

Table 7-11: Water Processing and Storage subsystem open issues status.

Typology	Description	Criticality	Resolution need date/event
INTERFACES (mechanical)	Mounting envelope constraints consolidation	medium	CDR
INTERFACES (electrical)	Definition of electrical connector part number	low	CDR
SUBSYSTEM UNIT	Definition of a safety filter for capturing steam from AC regeneration	medium	CDR

8 Water Quality and Condition Monitoring Subsystem

8.1 Baseline Design

8.1.1 General overview

Location of the Water Quality and Condition Monitoring subsystem is shown in Figure 8-1. It consists of two separate systems as shown in Table 8-1.

Figure 8-1: Location of the Water Quality and Condition Monitoring subsystem.

Table 8-1: Baseline equipment of Water Quality and Condition Monitoring Subsystem.

No.	Equipment	Function	Responsible part
1.	LIBS subsystem	Qualitative assessment of water quality, identification of elements present in water.	SW
2a.	EC sensor + Equipment	Active monitoring and control parameter for purification line	WUST
2b.	Sulphur sensors, absorbance sensor, turbidity sensor + Equipment	Condition monitoring for purification line	

Figure 8-2: Preliminary location of the Water Quality and Condition Monitoring subsystem on the rack.

The total dimensions of Quality & Condition Monitoring 1&2 will fit the spot on the shelf between the Data Acquisition & Control Subsystem and Purification Subsystem, the preliminary envelope is ~500x700x500mm + 700x400x300mm. Preliminary location of equipment is shown in Figure 8-2.

8.1.2 Water Quality and Condition Monitoring 1 – LIBS

8.1.2.1 Preliminary internal architecture

The Figure 8-3 presents the preliminary internal architecture and context of LIBS subsystem.

Figure 8-3: Preliminary internal architecture and system context of LIBS system.

8.1.2.2 Preliminary setup in the rack

As common envelope was reserved for Scanway’s and WUST’s hardware, the exact setup must be agreed with WUST.

Current setup assumptions:

- Piping shall be easily accessible, preferably placed in the front of the setup.
- Common hydraulic interface type and interface gender policy will be agreed with TAS and WUST.
- Laser shall be placed near the measurement cell, so that its optical window could be connected with measurement cell using the optical fibre not longer than 500 mm.
- Spectrometer shall be placed near the measurement cell, so that its optical window could be connected to measurement cell using the optical fibre not longer than 1000 mm.
- Components for which placement is not critical (PC, power supply, laser controller), may be placed in different location than measurement critical components.
- Designing setup as single box is desired.
- Setup shall meet laser safety rules.

8.1.2.3 Data

Raw spectrograms and logs will be saved locally on the PC with remote desktop (high data integrity required, at least 2 instances of data storage mediums in PC will be implemented, additional regular cloud backups will be considered).

Internet connection to the LIBS PC will be provided (Ethernet or WiFi – TBD) so it can be accessed remotely from Scanway Headquarters.

Table 8-2: Information exchanged between LIBS subsystem and Data acquisition and control subsystem.

No.	In/Out (LIBS PC perspective)	Signal type	Signal name	Information carried
1.	In	Logic flag	Trigger	High - measurement to be carried out in 30 TBD seconds
2.	Out	Logic flag	Laser on	High - Laser was activated and will fire within time window signaled by that signal
3.	Out	Logic flag	Valve closed	Physical feedback from valve control signal – valve normally open, high signal means that valve is closed (TBC)
4.	Out	Logic flag	Measurement OK	High – measurement finished; result is OK compared with specified requirements
5.	Out	Logic flag	Measurement not OK	High – measurement finished; result is NOT OK compared with specified requirements
6.	TBD	Logic flag	Placeholder	
7.	TBD	Logic flag	Placeholder	
8.	TBD	Logic flag	Placeholder	

8.1.2.4 Power

Scanway’s LIBS subsystem was agreed to be powered by:

- 230 VAC wall power outlet,
- 24 VDC from LUXWEX power system.

8.1.3 Quality & Condition Monitoring 2 – WUST

8.1.3.1 Preliminary internal architecture

WUST preliminary internal architecture is shown in Figure 8-4. The electroconductivity sensor is connected to the DLR Data Acquisition and Control subsystem. The rest of the sensors (turbidity, absorbance (TOC measurement), sulphide, sulphate) will be connected to the WUST PC.

The inlet and outlet ending will be built with PTFE tube (TBC) with 1/8” connectors and quick connector (gender to be established).

Measurement frequency is assumed as 1 measurement per 10 seconds for each sensor.

The working pressure is considered to be 1 bar.

Figure 8-4: General overview of the quality and condition monitoring 2 system.

The measuring cell will be made of PTFE plates in a way that allows to be able to perform maintenance tasks (e.g., take the entire set out of the rack for maintenance purposes). The exemplary assembly is shown below, Figure 8-5. Depending on the available volume the final design of the measuring cell will be determined (horizontal/vertical placement of pipeline).

Figure 8-5: Exemplary set-up of WUST measuring cell.

8.1.3.2 Preliminary setup in the rack

Preliminary setup is shown in Figure 8-2. As common envelope was reserved for Scanway’s and WUST’s hardware, the exact setup must be agreed with SW.

8.1.3.3 Data

Data from sulfide, sulfate, turbidity, and absorbance sensors will be saved on the WUST PC (cloud). Data from conductivity (EC) sensor will be transmitted to the DLR Data and Acquisition Control. The general flow of data is shown in the Figure 9.1-6.

Figure 8-6: General overview of the data flow in the quality and condition monitoring 2 system.

8.1.3.4 Power

230V to the computer and interface. Low voltage to the transmitter.

8.2 Options and Trade-offs

8.2.1 Points of LIBS measurement

Problem: Inline LIBS measurement in 3 points vs inline measurement in 1 point.

Solution: Inline LIBS measurement in 1 point (agreed by TAS, WUST and SW).

Rational: Design capable of LIBS measurement in 3 points but with single LIBS hardware (multiplication of measurement hardware is denied by the budget) would require complex solution possibly including hydraulic sample delivery, washing the measurement chambers, or implementing 3 measurement chambers and movable optical probe. Such a solution would be very complex and hard to implement in future space-graded system, especially considering redundancy demanded by reliability standards. Performing the water quality measurements in many points of the system is valid for development and testing reasons, so it does not back the need for LIBS inline measurement in 3 points.

8.2.2 Points of WUST measurement

Problem: WUST two-point measurement points WUST (before and purification line)

Description: WUST Quality. & Cond. Monitoring may consist of two measurement cells - before and after purification unit, while reducing the number of probes used (lack of absorption probe due to a large share in the budget). First measurement cell (before purification) would collect data regarding raw water composition during each experiment campaign regarding EC, turbidity, sulfate, sulfide (data collected by WUST). Second measurement cell (after purification) would measure and control EC in outlet stream (data collected and monitored by DLR), and collect data regarding turbidity, sulfate, and sulfide concentration (data collected by WUST).

Pros: This configuration would guarantee inline, online, constant monitoring of raw water composition. Data could be used for boarder description of the liquefaction process and behavior of ice-water.

Cons: Possible interference of measurement due higher concentration of components before purification line. Absorbance sensor (removed in this configuration) allows for online and constant monitoring of organic content in purified water. Appearance of the organics in the outlet

indicates a failure of the purification system. Addition of another measuring cell will increase complexity of the system.

Result for now: TAS will add EC sensor before purification unit, which allow for monitoring of the raw water conductance. Further discussion can be made in future meetings.

Figure 8-7: General overview of the quality and condition monitoring 2 system.

Figure 8-8: General overview of the quality and condition monitoring 2 system.

8.3 Open Issues

Table 8-3: Open issues list for SW and WUST.

Name	Description	Responsible
Placement of WUST and SW system in available space	Establishing how we are going to share the common envelope with the exact component	SW, WUST
Gender of water connectors	What kind of water connectors will be used.	TAS, SW, WUST
Water samples for probes and LIBS testing	To determine how the water samples will be transferred between TAS, DLR, SW, and WUST (or if we could do it by ourselves etc.)	TAS, DLR, SW, WUST

Name	Description	Responsible
Final design of the LIBS equipment and measuring cell		WUST, SW
Measurement of sulphur?	If the sulphur probes will be chosen we have to send them to TAS, or [...] testing it before experiment campaign TGS	TAS, WUST
Final components selection	To determine a probes producer etc. To decide if we need two sulphur probes.	WUST
Final design of the measuring cell	Depending on the available volume the final design of the measuring cell will be determined (horizontal/vertical)	WUST, SW
Probes maintenance protocol		WUST
Number of valves and their operation	Solenoid valves before and after WUST measuring cell serves as protection against drying out of the probes. If SW decides to remove solenoid valves, WUST will add one before measuring cell.	WUST, SW, DLR (Valves control)
Implementation details of logic lines to data acquisition for sulphide, sulphate, turbidity, and absorbance sensor		WUST
Final components selection for prototype test		SW
Evaluation of the need to operate the valve		SW
Implementation details of logic lines to data acquisition		SW
Confirmation whether we need error (out) or abort (in) signals?		SW
Laser safety of final device	(we have an expert onboard; we will do what needs to be done)	SW
Measurement cell design, Optical window vs optical fibres going directly into the measurement cell;		SW

9 Data Acquisition and Control Subsystem

9.1 Baseline Design

9.1.1 Overview

Each subsystem has multiple sensors and actuators that need to be powered, controlled and read out. For this reason, there will be interfaces between the subsystems and the Data Acquisition and Control Subsystem (DAQC). Figure 9-1 shows a flow chart of power, data and water flow with the according interfaces to each subsystem.

The dashed lines and labels indicate the responsible project partner for the shown process steps. The DAQC will link all those steps, collect data and distribute power.

9.1.2 Control and Power Supply

The DAQC subsystem includes a Central Control Box (CCB) and a Power Supply Unit (PSU). The purpose of the PSU is to supply components with 230 VAC (alternating current) and to transform the 230 VAC to 24 VDC (direct current). The CCB will run entirely on 24 VDC.

The CCB will then distribute the transformed 24 VDC to the components. It will be the interface for all analogue and digital signals that need to be processed by the DAQC software. A first draft of the CCB and PSU can be seen in Figure 9-2.

There will be at least two power supplies inside the PSU so the National Instruments (NI) chassis can be powered separately to the other components. This should secure the ongoing measurements in case of a failing actuator or sensor.

The CCB and PSU will be located in front of the rack, mounted at the wall to save space for the Water Quality and Condition Monitoring (WQCM) subsystems. Dimensions are approximately 600 x 300 x 600 mm and 600 x 300 x 250 mm for the CCB and PSU.

9.1.3 NI-Chassis and Modules

Inside of the chassis there will be modules for analogue and digital in- and outputs for example for temperature measurements. Relay modules will enable the software to switch specific sensors or actuators on and off.

Most modules have multiple signal channels (4, 8, 16) to connect to probes. There will be plug interfaces on the CCB to collect all the signal lines for each singular subsystem. From there on, they will be connected to the specific modules. The chassis will be connected via LAN or USB to the DAQC computer.

Figure 9-1: Flow chart with interfaces of water, data and power for all the subsystems.

Figure 9-2: First draft of the Central Control Box and Power Supply Unit.

9.1.4 DAQC Software

The DAQC and Control will be realized with a LabVIEW program running on the DAQC computer. Besides the LAN/USB connection to the CCB, there will be more connections to single components that can only be connected via LAN or USB directly to the computer.

Regarding the other subsystems, the TVAC will only be used as environment and will not be controlled by the DAQC software. Valves opening the vacuum chambers will have a fail save established by the TVAC software being able to overwrite the DAQC commands to keep the chamber shut if needed.

The Water Purification System (WPS) will use its own LabVIEW software, running in parallel to the DAQC software on the same computer and the WQCM subsystems will have their own computer which has to exchange data with the main DAQC software.

All the data will be stored locally in at least two different locations and saved in a cloud storage. The latter one also enables the transfer of data in between the different computers.

9.1.5 List of Sensors and Actuators

To ensure that the number of signal channels of the NI-modules is sufficient, a list of all sensors and actuators which will be connected to the CCB hardware was made. This list can be found in Appendix 11.1.

The current list is summarized in Table 10-2. Here, the total number of channels needed and some approximate ranges for many inputs and outputs is shown. Regular updates are expected.

Table 10-1: Overview on LabVIEW controlled sensor and actuator inputs and outputs.

Signal Type	I/O	Range	Amount
Analog	Output	4-20 mA	4
		0-5 VDC	1
	Input	4-20 mA	62
Digital	Output		20
	Input		7
Relay	Output		19
LAN	Input		1
USB	Input		1
No. of channels needed:			115

9.1.6 List of NI-Modules

To keep the budget and the space inside the CCB limited, the number and kind of modules need to be considered well. Appendix 11.2 shows a list of NI modules with information about the channels needed.

9.2 Options and Trade-offs

9.2.1 Single Software vs. separated Control of the Subsystems

Idea:

Collecting data and controlling all the subsystems from one single software and computer would simplify the measuring procedure and data accumulation. It would benefit future experiments by providing a ground layer of established hard- and software interaction, timing and problem solving.

Problem(s):

The TVAC software is already established and changes to it or the incorporation of it into another software would take too much time and effort. Since the TVAC will only be the environment and not gather valuable data for the experiments, this decision will probably not affect future lunar experiments. If pressure or temperature changes not measured by the Extraction/Capturing subsystem sensors do play a bigger role in the future, the data collected by the TVAC subsystem can be later drawn to comparison from the backup.

Moreover, Scanway will not be able to provide the LIBS control for the WQCM subsystem via a LabVIEW format. There will be a separate computer to acquire data and control the WQCM instruments. Nonetheless, a connection to the DAQC subsystem will be established, providing information if the measurement is good enough and some status information.

In addition to that, the WPS has to be tested in advance. Combining all control into a separate program enables detailed investigations before combining all subsystems. When combined, there are fewer problems expected while running both systems at the same time. Also, the program will be written in LabVIEW. This simplifies a future possible merge of both software.

Solution:

There will be several separated control software and computers. As listed above, this simplified the experiment while still enabling the most important data and status exchange. Detailed data that is not needed for an undisturbed experimentation process can be accessed and compared later on.

9.2.2 Where to save the data?

Problem(s):

Using separated software on different computers creates a need for a combined data backup. No experimentation data should get lost.

Solution:

By connecting every computer to the internet, a cloud storage can be created to have a combined data backup and exchange data between the computers.

While creating a LAN network with all computers would be too much of an effort, a cloud backup can be easily established with only a solid internet connection. In addition to that, there will be at least two backups on every computer in two separate locations.

All data has to be saved with time stamps for a correct evaluation of the experiment.

9.2.3 Valves after WQCM1

Idea:

WQCM1 might need a valve to create a controlled water flow/level for the LIBS measurement. How will it be controlled?

Problem(s):

WQCM2 probes should not run dry while in an experiment.

Solution:

A second valve can be placed after WQCM2. Both will be controlled simultaneously by WQCM computer. In the case that WQCM1 doesn't need the first valve, it will be removed and control over the second valve will go to DAQC software. Signal channels for both valves are considered within the channel number and sensors list.

9.2.4 Power Supply for the Experiment

Idea:

Which kind of power supply is needed for the experiment?

- 230 VAC for high power components
- 24 VDC for most sensors and actuators
- 12 VDC for some sensors and actuators

Solution:

The PSU will cover 230 VAC and transform this outlet current to 24 VDC. Currently, to have a uniform power distribution, there will not be a 12 VDC system and all sensors and actuators should be chosen as 24 VDC versions if possible.

There should be multiple AC to DC converters to have a separate power source for the NI-chassis.

9.2.5 Selection of NI-Modules

Idea:

The modules list in appendix 10-2 shows variants with different channel numbers. For this project, modules with a higher channel number can be preferred to save space and money. There are already some modules available, which were funded through other means by DLR.

Problem(s):

The shown selection (light blue) is based on the sensor and actuator list and provides channels for every required sensor and actuator. The price for all those modules would be approximately 11.821 € and a second chassis would be needed. This exceeds the budget.

Solutions:

1. Limiting the number of temperature modules to three:

Advantages

- Only one chassis needed
- Lower cost: 4.981 €

Disadvantages

- Lower spatial resolution for temperature measurements by Extraction and Capturing Subsystem (only 24 sensors instead of 50)

2. Changing the four analogue current outputs for actuators to analogue voltage outputs:

Advantages

- One less output module needed
- Four temperature modules fit
- Only one chassis needed
- lower cost: 5.591 €

Disadvantages

- Actuators have to be voltage compatible
- Medium spatial resolution for temperature measurements (only 32 sensors instead of 50)

It should be checked if 32 temperature sensors are sufficient and the currently current driven actuators are voltage compatible. This would be the most budget friendly option while still fitting inside a single chassis and is currently considered as the best option.

9.2.6 Positioning of CCB and PSU

The CCB and PSU take up much space. To save room for the WQCM subsystems, they can be placed outside of the rack, mounted at the wall with hinges to the right side making sure the transparent door opens all the way.

9.3 Open Issues

9.3.1 Frequent updates

The Sensor and Actuator list should be updated frequently if any changes occur. This might influence the choice of NI-Modules.

9.3.2 Choice of NI-Modules

Actuator signal type:

Currently, there are four current output channels (crucible heaters, gas control valve) and one voltage output channel (RO pump). It should be checked, if those can be combined into a singular module to save space inside the chassis and have a uniform way of handling adjustable actuators.

Temperature DAQ:

The Extraction and Capturing Subsystem temperature measurement sensors will use too many channels (50). Currently, there is room for 32 RTD (4-wire) channels. It has to be checked if this number is sufficient. If not, another way of collecting the temperature readings might be needed that is more budget friendly.

9.3.3 WQCM Computer

The communication protocol between the DAQC Computer and WQCM Computer has to be established. Currently, there are 7 planned digital input channels and 1 digital output channel for LIBS status signals and safety procedures.

9.3.4 Error handling

Until now, there has been no exchange about software safety procedures and error handling in case of a failing subsystem or a flawed communication between the devices. This has to be established in the future.

9.3.5 LabVIEW Version

For communication and data exchange between the different software applications and possible later on integration of LabVIEW SubVIs into a singular program, it would be best if all partners agree on a specific LabVIEW version for creating future compatible software.

9.3.6 Placement of the DAQC Computer

The location of the DAQC Computer is not yet fixed. While operating the TVAC, the user should be placed in the control room for occupational safety reasons. If the computer is placed near the TVAC, a suitable HDMI/display port cable or a remote desktop needs to be installed. If the computer is placed in the control room, the USB/LAN connection has to be established to the chassis.

10 Simulants

10.1 Regolith Simulant

For the experiments planned in LUXWEX, the LHS-1 lunar regolith simulant from the supplier Exolith Lab (Florida, USA) will be used. Detailed work on the regolith simulant is part of WP4.2 and is going to be described in detail in D4.4.

10.2 Raw Water Simulant

The composition of the raw water simulant considers the LCROSS data reported in Colaprete *et al.* (2010) and Gladstone *et al.* (2010). Table 10-1 lists the volatile concentrations relative to water in ppm as calculated by Holquist *et al.* (2021) and the conversion to grams per litre assuming a water density of $1 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

Table 10-1: Lunar volatiles concentrations relative to water Holquist *et al.* (2021).

Compound		Concentration	
		ppm	$\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ a)
Hydrogen Sulphide	H ₂ S	73000	138.21
Ammonia	NH ₃	26600	25.18
Sulphur Dioxide	SO ₂	14000	49.82
Ethylene	C ₂ H ₄	13700	21.36
Carbon Dioxide	CO ₂	9400	22.98
Methanol	CH ₃ OH	6700	11.93
Methane	CH ₄	2800	2.50
Hydrogen	H ₂	22500	2.53
Carbon Monoxide	CO	80900	125.89

a) calculated in this work.

10.2.1 Raw Water Simulant for Testing the Purification Subsystem

The composition of the raw water simulant for testing the purification subsystem shall mimic a water matrix expected after the cold-trap and liquefaction unit (see Chapter 0). Due to cooling of the cold trap by using the cold shroud in the TVAC, which is cooled with liquid nitrogen, the cold trap will operate at a temperature lower than the expected lunar operating temperature. As the cold trap temperature strongly influences the volatile concentrations, the cold trap design will be adjusted to operate as close as possible to the temperature reported by Holquist *et al.* (2021). Therefore, a raw water simulant will be prepared that assumes the concentrations after the lunar cold trap as given in Holquist *et al.* (2021) (Table 7). The raw water simulant neglects the volatiles expected to remain in the vapour phase in the cold trap.

Table 10-2: Composition of the raw water simulant (purification subsystem tests) (Holquist *et al.* (2021) Table 7).

Compound		Best Case		Worst Case	
		$\text{mol}_x \cdot \text{mol}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{-1}$	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ b)	$\text{mol}_x \cdot \text{mol}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{-1}$	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ b)
Hydrogen sulphide	H ₂ S	5.00E-10	9.47E-04	2.20E-09	4.17E-03
Ammonia	NH ₃	1.76E-07	1.67E-01	9.29E-07	8.79E-01
Sulphur dioxide	SO ₂	7.00E-10	2.49E-03	2.20E-08	7.83E-02
Ethylene	C ₂ H ₄	1.00E-10	1.56E-04	6.00E-10	9.35E-04
Carbon dioxide	CO ₂	3.00E-10	7.34E-04	3.00E-09	7.34E-03
Methanol	CH ₃ OH	2.10E-08	3.74E-02	1.50E-06	2.66E+00

b) calculated in this work assuming a water density of $1 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$

In addition, the raw water simulant shall contain $0.005 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of the LHS simulant ground to a particle size $<2 \mu\text{m}$.

10.2.2 Raw Water Simulant for testing the Process Chain inside the Vacuum Chamber

An additional raw water simulant is prepared to test the process chain from water extraction to liquefaction. Due to degradation of the vacuum chamber equipment, NH₃, SO₂ and H₂S cannot be added to the water simulant. Furthermore, CO is neglected due to health risks and H₂ and CH₄ because they are permanently

present as gases and have no influence on the process chain. Table 10-3 shows the concentrations of the water simulant that will be fed into the ice-regolith simulant production.

Table 10-3: Composition of the raw water simulant (process chain tests inside vacuum chamber).

Compound		Concentration g·L ⁻¹
Ethylene	C ₂ H ₄	21.36
Carbon Dioxide	CO ₂	22.98
Methanol	CH ₃ OH	11.93

The entire process chain, from water extraction to product water storage, will be tested with an ice regolith simulant containing ethylene, carbon dioxide and methanol at the concentrations listed in Table 10-3.

Note: At this stage, the potential risks of mixing the listed compound concentrations have not been investigated in detail. Thus, changes in the composition of the raw water simulants are possible. Detailed work on the raw water simulant production, assumptions and calculations is part of WP4.2 and details will be provided in D4.4.

10.3 Ice-Regolith Simulant

The Ice-regolith simulant is made by make ice particles out of the raw water simulant and mixing those particles with the regolith simulant under the presence of liquid nitrogen to maintain stable cold temperatures. Detailed work on the ice-regolith simulant is part of WP4.2 and is going to be described in detail in D4.4.

11 Appendix

11.1 List of Sensors and Actuators

Subsystem	Sensor/actuator name	Location	Controlled by	Amount	Sum	Connection type	Sampling frequency	Input to LabVIEW	Output needed from LabVIEW	Voltage	Comments optional
TVAC	mass spectrometer Pfeiffer 100	outside TVAC	LabVIEW	1	1	LAN	1 Hz	data	None?	?	
	Gas control valve EVR 136 (interface)	outside TVAC	LabVIEW	1	1	analog? / RS-232 C	1 Hz	None?	0-20mA?	24VDC	
Extraction & Capturing	Temperature sensor	inside TVAC	LabVIEW	50		analog	1-10Hz	0-10V? or 4-20mA	None	24VDC	
	Pressure sensor	outside TVAC	pressure reader	0		analog	1 Hz	None	None	24VDC	
	Pressure sensor	outside TVAC	pressure reader	0	51	analog	1 Hz	None	None	24VDC	
	Reader for pressure sensors TPG 366	outside TVAC	LabVIEW	1		usb		data	None?	250VAC	4x PS215/02TE, 2x PTR27000 pressure sensor
Actuators	Crucible heater	Crucible	LabVIEW	3	3	analog	1 Hz	None	0-20mA?	24VDC	
	Heating foil zones	inside TVAC	LabVIEW	4		digital to relay	1 Hz	None	on/off	24VDC	maybe 3 instead of 4
	Fast opening door	inside TVAC	manually	0	16	manually	1 Hz	None	None	None	fallsave with TVAC Software
	Valves	outside TVAC	LabVIEW	9		digital to relay	1 Hz	None	on/off	24VDC?	
Purification and Storage	Water Tank level sensor	Storage	LabVIEW	2		analog	1 Hz	RS232 or 4-20mA	None	230VAC	
	Differential pressure sensor	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	1		analog	1 Hz	4-20mA	None	24VDC	
	Pressure sensor	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	1		analog	1 Hz	4-20mA	None	24VDC	
	Conductivity indicator/transmitter	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	2	9	2x analog	1 Hz	4-20mA	None	24VDC	two sensors with two channels
	Temperature indicator	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	2		analog	1 Hz	4-20mA	None	24VDC	
	Flow meter	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	1		analog/digital	1 Hz	RS232 or 0-5 0-30V or 4-20mA	None	24VDC	
Actuators	Heater	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	1		digital to relay	1 Hz	None	on/off	24VDC	
	Catalytic oxidation reactor	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	1		digital to relay	1 Hz	None	on/off	24VDC	
	RO pump	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	1	5	digital to relay + analog	1 Hz	None	on/off + 0-5VDC	24VDC	for relay and analog usage
	Peristaltic pump	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	1		digital to relay	1 Hz	None	on/off	24VDC	
	Solenoid valve	Water Purification System	LabVIEW	1		digital to relay	1 Hz	None	on/off	24VDC	
	LIBS spectrometer	after Purification	WGCMI Computer	0		None	1 Hz	None	None	24VDC	Laser on, Valve closed, Measurement ok, measurement not ok, 3 spares
Quality and Condition Monitoring 1	LIBS Computer	LIBS Computer	LabVIEW	7	7	digital	1 Hz	on/off	None	24VDC / 7 230VAC	
	solenoid valve	after LIBS	WGCMI Computer	0		analog	1 Hz	None	None	24VDC	
	LIBS Computer	LIBS Computer	LabVIEW	1	1	digital	1 Hz	None	on/off	AC 230 24VDC / 7 230VAC	start measurement signal
Quality and Condition Monitoring 2	Naa Probe / Turbidity ?	after LIBS	WGCMI Computer	0		digital	1 Hz	None	None	24VDC	
	Absorbance probe (UV Light)	after LIBS	WGCMI Computer	0		digital	1 Hz	None	None	24VDC	
	Conductivity probe (interface MCA315/21)	after LIBS	LabVIEW	1	1	analog	1 Hz	4-20mA	None?	24VDC	
	Sulfide probe	after LIBS	WGCMI Computer	0		digital	1 Hz	None	None	24VDC	
	Sulfate/lead probe	after LIBS	WGCMI Computer	0		digital	1 Hz	None	None	24VDC	
	solenoid valve	before storage	WGCMI or LabVIEW	1	1	digital to relay	1 Hz	None	on/off	24VDC	normally open, might be controlled via WGCMI Computer
				Total (vs LabVIEW controlled Sensors)	69						
				Total (vs LabVIEW controlled Actuators)	24						

11.2 List of NI-Modules

List of Chassis		Number	Modules available	Amount to buy	Price	Comment						
		NI cDAQ-9188XT	2?		n.a	not in stock						
		NI cDAQ-9178	1		2.210,00 €							
List of Modules												
Type	Module Type	Signal Type	Channels	Range	Sampling rate	Channels needed	Modules needed	Spare Channels	Modules available	Amount to buy	Price	Comment
Current input	AI	A	8	±20 mA	200 kS/s	0	0	0	1	0	995,00 €	
	AI	A	16	±20 mA	500 S/s	12	1	4	0	1	1.260,00 €	
Current output	AO	A	4	0 - 20 mA	100 kS/s	0	0	0	0	0	705,00 €	
	AO	A	8	0 - 20 mA	24 kS/s	4	1	4	0	1	1.100,00 €	only D-SUB or screw terminal
Voltage output	AO	V	16	± 10 V	25 kS/s	1	1	15	2	0	1.780,00 €	too many spare channels
Temperature	AI	T	8	0 - 4000 Ω	400 S/s	50	7	6	2	5	1.710,00 €	maybe not via NI modules? Very expensive
Digital output	DO	V	8	12V/24v	100 µs	0	0	0	0	0	191,00 €	
	DO	V	32	12V/24v	500 µs	20	1	12	0	1	720,00 €	
Digital Input	D/DO	V	8	5V TTL	100 ns	0	0	0	0	0	545,00 €	only D-SUB
	DI	V	8	12V/24v	100 µs	7	1	1	0	1	191,00 €	less expensive, simple logic levels
USB												
LAN												
Relay												
Others												

12 References

- Al-Dawery, S.K. (2016), "Adsorption of methanol from methanol–water mixture by activated carbon and its regeneration using photo-oxidation process", *Desalination and Water Treatment*, Vol. 57 No. 7, pp. 3065–3073.
- Anthony, S.M., Jolley, S.T. and Captain, J.G. (2013), "Advanced Water Purification System for In Situ Resource Utilization", in *AIAA SPACE 2013 Conference and Exposition, San Diego, CA*, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Reston, Virginia.
- Boul, P., Lange, K. and Conger, B., et al. (2010), "Air Stripping Designs for the Lunar Surface", in *40th International Conference on Environmental Systems, Barcelona, Spain*, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Reston, Virginia.
- Colaprete, A., Schultz, P. and Heldmann, J., et al. (2010), "Detection of water in the LCROSS ejecta plume", *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, Vol. 330 No. 6003, pp. 463–468.
- Gladstone, G.R., Hurley, D.M. and Retherford, K.D., et al. (2010), "LRO-LAMP observations of the LCROSS impact plume", *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, Vol. 330 No. 6003, pp. 472–476.
- Guo, J., Lee, J.-G. and Tan, T., et al. (2019), "Enhanced ammonia recovery from wastewater by Nafion membrane with highly porous honeycomb nanostructure and its mechanism in membrane distillation", *Journal of Membrane Science*, Vol. 590, p. 117265.
- Holquist, J.B., Gellenbeck, S. and Bower, C.E., et al. (2021), "Experimental Proof of Concept of a Cold Trap as a Purification Step for Lunar Water Processing", in *50th International Conference on Environmental Systems, virtual, 12.-15. July*.
- Huisman, I.H. (2000), "MEMBRANE SEPARATIONS | Microfiltration", in *Encyclopedia of Separation Science*, Elsevier, pp. 1764–1777.
- Hurtado, C.F. and Cancino-Madariaga, B. (2014), "Ammonia retention capacity of nanofiltration and reverse osmosis membranes in a non steady state system, to be use in recirculation aquaculture systems (RAS)", *Aquacultural Engineering*, Vol. 58, pp. 29–34.
- Jurado, N.I. (2021), "Rarefied Water Vapor Deposition From Icy Lunar Regolith On An Engineered Cold Plate", University of Texas at El Paso, El Paso, Texas, 2021.
- Kiewiet, L., Hab, N.M. and Marchese, F.M., et al. (2022), "Trade-off and optimization for thermal Lunar water extraction system", in *73rd International Astronautical Congress (IAC), 18-22 September*.
- Liu, Y., Wang, C. and Pang, Y., et al. (2023), "Water extraction from icy lunar regolith by drilling-based thermal method in a pilot-scale unit", *Acta Astronautica*, Vol. 202, pp. 386–399.
- Nelson, R., Flakker, C. and Muggli, D. (2007), "Photocatalytic oxidation of methanol using titania-based fluidized beds", *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, Vol. 69 No. 3-4, pp. 189–195.
- van de Beld, L., Bijl, M. and Reinders, A., et al. (1994), "The catalytic oxidation of organic contaminants in a packed bed reactor", *Chemical Engineering Science*, Vol. 49 No. 24, pp. 4361–4373.
- Yang, Q., Li, Z. and Lv, W., et al. (2013), "On the laboratory and field studies of removing fine particles suspended in wastewater using mini-hydrocyclone", *Separation and Purification Technology*, Vol. 110, pp. 93–100.